

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ESCHERICHIA COLI: THE MAIN CAUSE OF URINARY INFECTIONS

Regina Ristić

MD, Specialist in Medical Laboratory Diagnostics, Biotest Laboratory
Institute, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Abstract

Introduction: Urinary tract infections are most commonly caused by the uropathogenic bacterium *Escherichia coli* (UPEC), primarily affecting otherwise healthy women (50% of women will experience a urinary tract infection). These infections can become chronic and are highly recurrent.

Objective: To compare the frequency of urinary infections caused by *E. coli* with those caused by other pathogenic bacteria.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted at the Biotest Laboratory Institute in Novi Sad. Data were obtained from archives for the period from January 2, 2023, to December 31, 2023. A total of 10,624 patients were included in the study. Of the total number of patients, 2,143 samples were positive for bacteria, representing 20% of the total number of analyses, while 8,499 samples were negative for bacterial presence in urine, representing 80% of the total number of patients tested.

Results: Of the 2,143 samples positive for bacterial presence in urine: 1,740 samples had gram-negative bacteria isolated, and 403 samples had gram-positive bacteria isolated. This indicates that gram-negative bacteria were isolated in a large number of patients (81%), while gram-positive bacteria were isolated in 19% of patients. Of the 1,740 samples with isolated gram-negative bacteria: 1,392 samples had *Escherichia coli*, 224 samples had *Klebsiella*, 88 samples had *Proteus*, and 36 samples had other gram-negative bacteria. This shows that uropathogenic *E. coli* strains are by far the most common cause of urinary infections, representing 80% of the total number of gram-negative cultures. *Klebsiella* follows with 13%, *Proteus* with 5%, and other gram-negative bacteria with 2%.

Conclusion: Urinary tract infections, encompassing various infectious etiologies, represent a significant threat to human health. Urinary tract infections are most commonly caused by the uropathogen *Escherichia coli*.

Keywords: urinary infections, bacteria, *Escherichia coli*.

1. Introduction

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) represent a significant burden on healthcare systems. UTIs (i) are most commonly caused by the uropathogenic bacterium *Escherichia coli* (UPEC), (ii) primarily affect otherwise healthy women (50% of women will experience a urinary tract infection), (iii) are associated with significant morbidity and economic impact, (iv) can become chronic, and (v) are highly recurrent. A history of UTIs is a significant risk factor for recurrent UTIs (rUTIs). In otherwise healthy women, an acute urinary tract infection results in a 25 to 50% chance of reinfection within a few months of the initial infection. Interestingly, rUTIs are usually caused by the same strain of *E. coli* that led to the initial infection, indicating that there are reservoirs associated with the host, such as the gastrointestinal tract and urinary bladder tissue. (1)

Bacterial urinary tract infections present with various signs and symptoms and can be caused by a range of organisms. This review primarily focuses on uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) as the etiological agent of urinary tract infections. (2)

2. Objective

The aim of this study is to analyze the most common causative agents of urinary infections, specifically to statistically process data to determine which bacteria most frequently cause urinary infections, based on bacteriological urine tests (urine cultures) from the Biotest

Laboratory Institute for the period from January 2, 2023, to December 31, 2023.

3. Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at the Biotest Laboratory Institute in Novi Sad. The data used were obtained from the archive of microbiological findings of patients. The investigation was carried out from January 2, 2023, to December 31, 2023. The study included 10,624 patients. Of the total number of patients, 2,143 samples were positive for bacteria, representing 20% of the total number of analyses, while 8,499 samples were negative for bacterial presence in urine, representing 80% of the total number of patients tested.

Urine culture involves a bacteriological examination of urine, which is performed exclusively from a sample provided in a sterile container. (3)

When working with microorganisms, it is desirable to work with pure cultures. Urine is inoculated onto specific nutrient media. After an incubation period, bacterial colonies appear on the surface of the agar that are visible to the naked eye. The advantage of solid media is that the procedure allows microorganisms to grow as separate, individual colonies, thereby simplifying the acquisition of pure cultures. (4)

4. Results

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are one of the most common bacterial infections, primarily affecting women. (5)

Uropathogenic strains of *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) cause the majority of UTIs in otherwise healthy women. (6)

Based on the analysis of bacteriological urine tests (urine cultures) from the Biotest Laboratory Institute for the period from January 2, 2023, to December 31, 2023, the following results were obtained:

During the observed period, 10,624 patients were included in the study. Of the total number of patients,

2,143 samples were positive for bacteria, representing 20% of the total number of analyses, while 8,499 samples were negative for bacterial presence in urine, representing 80% of the total number of patients tested.

From this ratio, it is evident that the number of positive bacterial analyses is significantly lower than the number of negative analyses.

Figure 1. Ratio of Positive and Negative Urine Samples from the Biotest Laboratory Institute for the Period from January 2, 2023, to December 31, 2023

From the 2,143 samples that were positive for the presence of bacteria in urine:

In 1,740 samples, gram-negative bacteria were isolated,

In 403 samples, gram-positive bacteria were isolated,

This indicates that gram-negative bacteria were isolated in a large number of patients (81%), while

gram-positive bacteria were isolated in 19% of patients. This ratio of gram-negative to gram-positive bacteria shows that gram-negative bacteria are far more common causes of urinary infections compared to gram-positive bacteria.

Figure 2. Ratio of Urine Culture Samples with Isolated Gram-Positive and Gram-Negative Bacteria

In 1,392 samples, *Escherichia coli* was isolated,
 In 224 samples, *Klebsiella* was isolated,
 In 88 samples, *Proteus* was isolated, and

In 36 samples, other gram-negative bacteria were isolated,

This shows that uropathogenic strains of *E. coli* are by far the most common causes of urinary infections, representing 80% of the total number of gram-

negative cultures. *Klebsiella* follows with 13%, *Proteus* with 5%, and other gram-negative bacteria with 2%.

Of the 1,740 samples with isolated gram-negative bacteria:

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) have a complex dynamic, with uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) being the main causative agent. UPEC is capable of colonizing from the urethra to the kidneys in extracellular and intracellular niches, simultaneously causing chronic persistent infections and frequent disease recurrences. (7)

Relapse is defined as an infection caused by the same strain as the initial infecting strain, while reinfection represents an infection caused by a different strain. (8)

The lifetime risk of UTIs in women is high (greater than 50%). (9)

From the above, it can be observed that *E. coli* is the main cause of urinary infections. Figure 3. Ratio of Gram-Negative Bacteria Isolated in 1,740 Urine Samples

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is one of the most common bacterial infections, accounting for 0.9% of all outpatient visits to doctors. (10)

5. Discussion

In our study conducted at the Biotest Laboratory Institute from January 2, 2023, to December 31, 2023, a total of 10,624 patients were included. Of these, 2,143 samples were positive for bacteria, representing 20% of the total number of analyses, while 8,499 samples were negative for bacterial presence in urine, representing 80% of the total number of patients tested. Of the 2,143 samples that were positive for bacteria in urine: 1,740 samples had gram-negative bacteria isolated, and 403 samples had gram-positive bacteria isolated.

Of the 1,740 samples with isolated gram-negative bacteria: 1,392 samples had *Escherichia coli* isolated, which accounts for 80%. A study by Mat S. Conover and colleagues found that uropathogenic *Escherichia*

coli (UPEC) accounts for more than 85% of reported urinary tract infections. (11)

Similarly, a study conducted by Ejrnaels found that *Escherichia coli* is the most dominant pathogen, causing 80-90% of urogenital tract infections. (12)

6. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of bacteriological urine tests (urine cultures) from the Biotest Laboratory Institute for the period from January 2, 2023, to December 31, 2023, we have reached the following conclusions:

During the observed period, 10,624 patients were included in the study. Of these, 2,143 samples were positive for bacteria, representing 20% of the total number of analyses, while 8,499 samples were negative for bacterial presence in urine, representing 80% of the total number of patients tested.

Of the 2,143 samples that were positive for bacteria in urine:

1,740 samples had gram-negative bacteria isolated,

403 samples had gram-positive bacteria isolated.

Of the 1,740 samples with isolated gram-negative bacteria:

1,392 samples had *Escherichia coli* isolated,

224 samples had *Klebsiella* isolated,

88 samples had *Proteus* isolated, and

36 samples had other gram-negative bacteria isolated.

From these results, we can conclude that *E. coli* is the primary causative agent of urinary infections, both globally and locally.

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